

Isotopic Evidence for a Cold and Distant Origin of 3I/ATLAS

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Abstract

Interstellar objects provide the only directly observable samples of icy planetesimals formed around other stars, and can therefore provide insight into the diversity of physical and chemical conditions occurring during exoplanet formation [1–3]. Here we report isotopic measurements of the interstellar comet 3I/ATLAS, which reveal an elemental composition unlike any Solar System body. The water in 3I/ATLAS is enriched in deuterium, at a level of $D/H = (0.98 \pm 0.06)\%$, which is more than an order of magnitude higher than in known comets, while its range of $^{12}C/^{13}C$ ratios (141–191 for CO_2 and 123–172 for CO) exceeds typical values found in the Solar System, as well as nearby interstellar clouds and protoplanetary disks. Such extreme isotopic signatures indicate formation at temperatures $\lesssim 30$ K in a relatively metal-poor environment. When interpreted with respect to models for Galactic chemical evolution, the carbon isotopic composition implies that 3I/ATLAS may have accreted as long ago as 12 billion years, following a period of intense, early star formation. 3I/ATLAS thus represents a preserved fragment of an ancient planetary system.

Keywords: Comets; 3I/ATLAS; Interstellar Objects; Infrared Spectroscopy; Composition; Isotopic Ratios; Galactic Chemical Evolution

3I/ATLAS is the third confirmed interstellar object to pass through our inner Solar System [4]. It exhibited surprisingly high gas production rates around perihelion, which have enabled detailed spectroscopic investigations [3, 5–7]. However, its exact time and

place of origin, and the history of its path through the Galaxy, remain highly uncertain [8–10]. A broad range of ages (3–11) Gyr was deduced based on its high velocity, but tracing the orbital trajectory back more than ~ 10 Myr is difficult due to unpredictable (chaotic) gravitational interactions within the inhomogeneous Galactic environment [11]. Isotopic ratio measurements provide invaluable insights into the physical and chemical conditions where 3I/ATLAS formed [12]: the D/H ratio is sensitive to the temperature and radiation environment [13], while the $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio reveals the degree of heavy-element enrichment (metallicity), which helps constrain the location (in space and time) of its natal interstellar gas cloud [14].

1 JWST and ALMA Observations

We obtained infrared spectral imagery of 3I/ATLAS using the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) during the outbound leg of its 2025 perihelion passage. We simultaneously targeted emission lines from gas-phase water, carbon dioxide, and carbon monoxide (major isotopologues), in addition to their respective (deuterium and ^{13}C -bearing) minor isotopologues, allowing the derivation of precise isotopic ratios. The $2.7\ \mu\text{m}$ H_2O fundamental rovibrational bands were observed on 2025-Dec-22, with a subsequent, deeper integration covering H_2O (hot bands), HDO, CO_2 , $^{13}\text{CO}_2$, CO and ^{13}CO between $3.6\text{--}5.0\ \mu\text{m}$ on 2025-Dec-23 (see Methods for details). A summary of the observed molecular bands is given in Extended Data Table 1. For the purpose of measuring the coma expansion velocity, complementary, ground-based submillimeter-wave observations of 3I/ATLAS’s CO and HCN emission were obtained using the Atacama Compact Array (ACA — a subsystem of the Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array, ALMA) on 2025-Dec-22 (see Methods). 3I/ATLAS was at a heliocentric distance $r_H \approx 2.4$ au for all observations.

Multiple spectral lines from each of the major isotopologues were detected across the entirety of the NIRSpc field of view, confirming the presence of a spatially extended gas coma, with a peak intensity at the assumed position of the nucleus (the pseudo-nucleus). The image cubes for the major isotopologues were baseline-subtracted using a polynomial fit to the surrounding continuum regions in each pixel, then spectrally integrated to produce the molecular emission maps shown in Fig. 1. Spatially-integrated spectra (within a $d = 3.6''$ -diameter circular aperture centered on the pseudo-nucleus) are shown for all the species of interest in Fig. 2.

Gas production rates (Q), rotational temperatures (T_{rot}), and isotopic ratios were derived by modeling the observed infrared emission lines as a function of sky-projected nucleocentric distance (ρ) using the Planetary Spectrum Generator (PSG [15]) (see Methods). The resulting Q_ρ curves for CO_2 and CO (Extended Data Fig. 1) reach a clear asymptote (“terminal” Q value) at $\rho \sim 0.3''$ (~ 400 km), indicating a lack of significant gas production for these species at larger radii, consistent with the majority of their outgassing arising directly from the nucleus. H_2O shows a significant increase in Q_ρ between $\rho \sim 0.3''\text{--}1.7''$ ($\sim 500\text{--}2,200$ km), consistent with a contribution to the H_2O gas production from icy grain sublimation in the coma; uniformity of the HDO/ H_2O ratio with radius (within the errors) implies similar gas release mechanisms for both H_2O and HDO.

Fig. 1: Spectrally integrated line flux maps for 3I/ATLAS observed using JWST NIRSpec. (a) H₂O at 2.7 μm, (b) CO₂ at 4.3 μm, (c) CO at 4.7 μm. Image axes are aligned with the equatorial (RA/decl.) grid. Molecular emission has been isolated by subtracting a polynomial fit to the adjacent continuum. Spatial coordinates are with respect to the brightest pixel in each map (the pseudo-nucleus). Inset panels (upper right) show the continuum-subtracted spectra within the image integration wavelength range, spatially integrated within a 3'' diameter circular aperture centered on the pseudo-nucleus (corresponding to 3,900 km at the 1.8 au distance of the comet from the telescope). Lower left corner shows the direction of the (sky-projected) comet-Sun (S) and nucleus velocity (*v*) vectors.

Fig. 2: Observed NIRSpec molecular spectra of 3I/ATLAS. Spectra have been integrated within a $d = 3.6''$ -diameter circular aperture centered on the pseudo-nucleus. Similarly spatially-integrated, best-fitting spectral models are overlaid, with (observation minus model) residuals in the lower sub-panels. As shown by the grey filled regions in panel (a), the strong CO ($v = 1 - 0$) lines were subtracted prior to fitting, to reduce spectral contamination when fitting H₂O. The grey region in panel (d) indicates wavelengths excluded (masked) from the fitting due to potential contamination by an unidentified feature around $4.42 \mu\text{m}$. In panel (f), the regions surrounding the stronger CO lines (shown in grey) were masked during ¹³CO fitting, to avoid contamination by the CO model residuals, and to allow improved fitting of the higher- J CO lines, some of which overlap ¹³CO. For panels (d) and (f), 5th-order baseline fits are shown; see Extended Data Fig. 3 for the ensemble of baselines used in deriving our final range of plausible ¹²C/¹³C values for these species.

Terminal gas production rates (Q_i) were calculated for each species from the average of the Q_ρ values in the 5 outermost annuli shown in Extended Data Fig. 1, and are given in Extended Data Table 1. From these production rates, we find the following mixing ratios (and 1σ statistical uncertainties) for the main coma gas constituents within the JWST field of view: $\text{CO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O} = 1.08 \pm 0.03$; $\text{CO}/\text{H}_2\text{O} = 2.40 \pm 0.07$; $\text{CO}/\text{CO}_2 = 2.24 \pm 0.01$. Since the earlier 2025-Aug-06 JWST observations [5] (obtained

at $r_H = 3.32$ au inbound), the coma $\text{CO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ratio has fallen by a factor of ≈ 7 , while the $\text{CO}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and CO/CO_2 ratios have increased by factors of ≈ 1.4 and ≈ 10 , respectively. This corresponds to a transition from a CO_2 -dominated to a CO -dominated coma during the object’s passage past the Sun (bracketing a likely H_2O -dominated phase around perihelion [6]), indicating a remarkable temporal evolution of the relative outgassing rates for these coma gases.

From the simultaneously-measured $Q_t(\text{HDO})$ and $Q_t(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ values (see Methods), we derive a D/H mixing ratio for water of $(0.98 \pm 0.06)\%$. Spectral baseline definition is more challenging for $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ and ^{13}CO than HDO, so for those species we report the results considering an ensemble of best-fitting Q_t values across a range of plausible baseline models (the associated data are given in Extended Data Tables 2 and 3), resulting in $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} = 141\text{--}191$ for CO_2 and $123\text{--}172$ for CO . These ranges include the (additive) statistical $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ uncertainties of 2% for CO_2 and 8% for CO , and should therefore be interpreted as the range of plausible fit parameters for each molecule.

2 Interpreting the isotopic ratios

The D/H and $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios for 3I/ATLAS are both extremely unusual among previously observed comets and other Solar System objects (Fig. 3). Although previous measurements of the $^{12}\text{CO}_2/^{13}\text{CO}_2$ ratio have been obtained in only two comets (67P and C/2017 K2), the $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio of the broader reservoir of volatile carbon in the Solar System (including other cometary gases), is well characterised. Observations of CH_4 in Jupiter, Saturn and Neptune, CO_2 on Mars and Venus, CH_4 ice on Eris and Makemake, as well as carbonates (and insoluble organic matter; IOM) in meteorites, and CN and C_2 in comets, all show remarkably similar $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios, consistent with terrestrial sedimentary rocks ($^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} = 89.4$), to within a few per cent, while the Solar ratio is 93.5 ± 0.7 [32]. The elevated $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios in 3I/ATLAS are therefore completely distinct from other materials measured in the Solar System, thus highlighting a non-local origin. The unusual isotopic ratios are supported by the findings of Salazar Manzano et al. [33] and Opitom et al. (submitted), who also found elevated D/H and $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios for 3I/ATLAS based on their respective ALMA and VLT observations (see Supplementary Discussion for further details).

Even outside the Solar System, measurements of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} > 100$ are rare, although such high ratios are predicted (and occasionally observed) in the outer parts of the Galaxy [14, 28, 29, 34]. The primary source of carbon in our Galaxy is from nucleosynthesis in the envelopes of asymptotic giant branch (AGB) stars, with additional, minor contributions from novae and supernovae [14, 35, 36]. Over their lifetimes, intermediate-mass AGB stars return material to the interstellar medium with increasingly-elevated elemental ^{13}C abundances, due to the conversion of ^{12}C to ^{13}C during hot bottom burning (*via* the CN cycle). Consequently, the cycle of star formation and death leads to increasing metallicity and decreasing $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios in the interstellar medium as a function of Galactic age [14]. In particular regions where non-equilibrium chemistry can prevail, molecular $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios are subject to further modulation, as a result of isotope-selective photodissociation and low-temperature chemical kinetics [12, 37–39]. These processes can either deplete or enhance the

Fig. 3: Galactic and Solar System Isotopic ratios. Observed isotopic ratio in the coma of 3I/ATLAS compared with Galactic and Solar System observations for D/H (a) and $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ (b). Data are from the compilation of Nomura et al. [12], with additional D/H values for 12P/Pons-Brooks [16], V883 Ori (gas-phase [17]), and IRAS20126+4104, HOPS370 and L1527 (ice-phase [18, 19]). D/H data are for H_2O unless otherwise specified. The “disks HCN” data represent the mean and range of observed D/H values across five protoplanetary disks. “MYSOs” data is the mean and range for massive young stellar objects. For $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$, the range of plausible fit results (including 1σ statistical errors) is given for 3I/ATLAS. The meteoritic “XCO₃” and “IOM” data are the mean values (and ranges) for carbonates and insoluble organic matter, respectively, in carbonaceous chondrites [20–22]. We also plot TW Hya and HD 163296 CO isotopic ratios [23, 24], mean protostellar ice CO and CO₂ values [25], protostellar CO gas (mean and range) [26], interstellar CO₂ ice (mean and range) [27], interstellar HCO⁺ isotopic ratios for two Galactocentric distances (r_G) [28], $r_G = 14$ kpc CN data [29], super-Jupiter exoplanet CO data [30], and M dwarf GJ745 data [31]. Error bars are 1σ unless otherwise specified.

$^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios in hydrocarbons and nitriles, yet their impact on the $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio in CO — the main carbon reservoir in dense interstellar clouds — is typically small. The relative insensitivity of interstellar CO and CO₂ ice to isotopic fractionation processes at low temperatures contributes to the relative consistency of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios across the Solar System. Consequently, the $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio in primitive planetary (and cometary) materials, including CO, CO₂ and their chemical derivatives, is thought to be close to the interstellar elemental value at the time of formation of the host star.

The elemental abundances observed in 3I/ATLAS place strict requirements on the chemical profile of its originating star-system, which, combined with dynamical constraints from the object’s Galactic orbit (deduced from its inbound velocity vector), result in a set of criteria that help isolate its origin in space and time — see Supplementary Discussion (and Supplementary Table 1) for further details.

In a sample of 63 nearby solar-type stars, $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios were measured in the range 71–105 [40]. Based on their ages, which span ~ 0 –9 Gyr, a relatively rapid onset of ^{13}C enrichment was inferred, during the first 4 Gyr of our Galaxy’s evolution, as a consequence of ^{13}C production in novae [41]. The resulting, steep $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ curve at early times in their model with 3–8 M_{\odot} white-dwarf nova progenitors (see Supplementary Figure 1), constrains the isotopic age of 3I/ATLAS to the range 11–12 Gyr, assuming an origin in the nearby Galactic disk. For comparison, the secondary $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ peak at metallicity $\log_{10}[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.5$ in Fig. 19 of Kobayashi et al. [14] (thick-disk model), corresponds to a similar estimated age of ~ 11 Gyr.

Uncertainties in the modeled $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios as a function of time are significant due to incomplete knowledge of the stellar initial mass function, star formation rates as a function of time (and Galactocentric radius), interstellar gas infall/outflow rates and stellar nucleosynthetic yields. A conclusive age estimate for 3I/ATLAS is further complicated by the interstellar $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ gradient as a function of Galactocentric distance [28, 29, 42] (see Supplementary Discussion). Ultimately, $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios within the range of plausible $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ fit values for 3I/ATLAS can be most readily explained as a result of temporal evolution of the interstellar $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio, with a possible additional contribution from the Galactic radial $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ gradient.

The D/H ratio for water in 3I/ATLAS demonstrates a surprisingly high deuterium enrichment compared with other (icy and non-icy) Solar System bodies and protostars within the Galaxy (Fig. 3a). The value of $(0.98 \pm 0.06)\%$ lies 15σ above the mean D/H of 0.029% in Solar System comets (where σ is the combined standard deviation of the data), and 10σ above the mean water D/H of 0.1% found in the total sample of high and low-mass protostars. Within the Solar System, only Venus’ atmosphere has a higher D/H, which results from mass-dependent atmospheric escape over the planet’s lifetime [43]. By contrast, the deuteration of H₂O ice in Solar System comets is theorised to occur primarily in the interstellar and pre-stellar phases, where H₂O is rapidly synthesised on the surfaces of dust grains at very low temperatures ($\lesssim 30$ K) [44, 45]. Jensen et al. [13] showed that water deuteration occurs efficiently in star-forming regions as long as the dust temperatures remain below 20–30 K, while increased ultraviolet radiation fields and cosmic ray ionisation rates actually accelerate the reactions responsible for deuterating H₂O; a high D/H ratio $\sim 1\%$ is achieved in

the presence of a cosmic ray flux $\gtrsim 10$ times the local Galactic value. Such enhanced-ionisation conditions would be expected in the vicinity of the lower-metallicity region of early, intense star-formation indicated by the high $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio and high abundances of C and O (α elements) in 3I/ATLAS. Several other properties of low-metallicity environments are theorised to accelerate the deuteration of H_2O ice, as summarised in the Supplementary Discussion.

A systematic difference is observed between the $\text{HDO}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ratios in nearby protostellar envelopes and those found in Solar System comets (Fig. 3a). Although the number statistics are small for clustered and isolated protostars, the lower D/H ratios in clustered environments can be attributed to higher temperatures and a shorter, low-temperature protostellar collapse phase, that leads to inhibited D enrichment [13]. The D/H ratio in Solar System comets may have been further reduced by thermochemical reprocessing of water in the disk, as a consequence of radial mixing or sublimation and re-freezing, resulting in the incorporation of re-equilibrated H_2O (with a lower D/H) back into the ice, thus lowering the bulk D/H ratio [46]. The exceptionally high D/H ratio measured in 3I/ATLAS therefore implies H_2O ice formation at very cold temperatures in an irradiated interstellar or protostellar environment, followed by a lack of significant, high-temperature reprocessing of its water in the disk. Although molecular ice and planetesimal formation is expected to be less efficient in reduced metallicity environments [47, 48], the HDO-rich composition of 3I/ATLAS proves that the cold, ice-rich conditions required for cometary accretion can still be maintained in less metal-rich (^{13}C -depleted) disks.

3 Conclusion

JWST observations of the interstellar comet 3I/ATLAS have revealed exceptionally high D/H and $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios in its coma. The observed elemental and isotopic abundance profile places strong constraints on the temperature and star-formation history of its originating environment. To obtain $\text{D}/\text{H} = 0.98\%$, the bulk of 3I/ATLAS's H_2O ice must have formed at temperatures $\lesssim 30$ K, with minimal contamination from water (re-)processed at higher temperatures. Its old, ^{13}C -poor natal environment was most likely embedded in a strongly-irradiated, interstellar cloud at relatively low metallicity, but enriched in C and O (and to lesser extents, N and S) in the aftermath of an intense period of massive star formation. Its distant origin in space and time makes 3I/ATLAS a uniquely-valuable tool for Galactic archaeology, highlighting the potential for interstellar object studies to help reveal the broader physical and chemical history of the Milky Way.

Methods

JWST Observations

Observations of 3I/ATLAS were performed using the JWST NIRSpec integral field unit (IFU) [49], as part of program ID 5094. The G235H dispersive element was used for a single 642 s exposure starting UT 2025-12-22 03:36, covering wavelengths $\lambda = 1.7\text{--}3.2\ \mu\text{m}$, followed by 5×700 s exposures with the G395H disperser starting UT 2025-12-23 08:07, covering $\lambda = 2.9\text{--}5.3\ \mu\text{m}$. The resulting 30×30 array of spectra have a resolving power $R_\lambda = \lambda/\Delta\lambda \sim 2700$ and a pixel size of $0.1''$, which is approximately the same as the FWHM of the JWST point-spread function at $3\ \mu\text{m}$.

3I/ATLAS was acquired and tracked in the IFU using JPL Horizons ephemeris solution #42. During observations, the object was 1.80 au from the telescope, at $r_H = 2.37\text{--}2.42$ au, with a (Sun-target-observer) phase angle of $22.7^\circ\text{--}21.6^\circ$. Each exposure was divided across four dither positions, spatially separated (in the approximate shape of a square) with offsets of $\approx 0.2''$ from the (central) targeted position. The data were reduced using the JWST Calibration Pipeline software version v1.20.2 [50] using the JWST Calibration Reference Data System context file 1464. The multiple dithers for each exposure were shifted and combined in the rest frame of the comet during image processing, thus allowing detector artifacts and cosmic ray events to be identified and removed. For each 3I/ATLAS exposure, a set of sky background exposures with matching exposure time, disperser and dither settings was obtained, offset by $300''$ from the science target, along the horizontal axis of the IFU aperture. Unfortunately, two of the five background exposures for G395H failed due to guide-star acquisition issues; these exposures will be re-observed later in 2026. Inspection of the available background exposures showed no evidence for significant emission from any background (*e.g.* interstellar) infrared sources or zodiacal light, so the final science data cubes were reduced without background subtraction in order to maximise the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

After centering on the comet, the individual exposures were combined and rebinned onto a common spatial-spectral coordinate system using the 3D drizzle algorithm included as part of the JWST pipeline’s `cube_build` task [51]. The resulting image cube spatial dimensions were $\approx 3.7'' \times 3.5''$ for G235H and $\approx 4.4'' \times 4.0''$ for G395H. The absolute flux calibration accuracy of the final data cubes is expected to be 3%.¹

To produce spectrally integrated emission maps, the observed data cubes in the vicinity of each emission band were first continuum-subtracted (pixel-by-pixel), using polynomial fits to the spectral baseline regions surrounding the detected emission lines. For H_2O , a 7th-order polynomial was used (fitted between $2.55\text{--}2.90\ \mu\text{m}$); for CO_2 , 1st order was used (fitted between $4.188\text{--}4.500\ \mu\text{m}$, with the $\text{CO}_2\ \nu_3$ band masked between $4.20\text{--}4.44\ \mu\text{m}$); for CO , 4th order was used (fitted between $4.50\text{--}4.85\ \mu\text{m}$). Spectral line emission was excluded from the continuum fits using an iterative sigma-clipping algorithm with a rejection threshold 2.8 times the residual RMS. The detected line emission was then spectrally integrated to produce the maps in Fig. 1. Although the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) per pixel was too low to allow useful mapping of the minor

¹<https://jwst-docs.stsci.edu/jwst-calibration-status/nirspec-calibration-status/nirspec-ifu-calibration-status>

isotopologues (HDO and ^{13}CO), significant emission from these species is detected in larger extraction apertures (see Fig. 2).

Astrometry

In order to guarantee the acquisition of 3I/ATLAS within the small ($3'' \times 3''$) NIR-Spec IFU field of view, while allowing for the $0.2''$ dither offsets and $0.1''$ telescope blind pointing accuracy, we had to ensure an ephemeris accuracy better than $\pm 1.2''$ (at 3σ confidence). To reach such a high accuracy, we performed astrometric measurements of 3I/ATLAS in the weeks leading up to our JWST observations using images contributed by observers at various professional telescope facilities, located at sites with good seeing conditions (see Acknowledgements for further details). These included the Canada-France-Hawai'i Telescope, Lowell Discovery Telescope, Apache Point Observatory (APO), Southern Astrophysical Research telescope, the Las Cumbres Observatory, and the University of Hawai'i 2.2 m telescope. Good seeing was essential to resolve the inner coma and the pseudo-nucleus with the greatest possible precision, ensuring a positional measurement as close as possible to the actual location of the cometary nucleus.

In the presence of asymmetric outgassing, the inner coma is often distorted in an antisolar direction, and most common astrometric centroiding procedures tend to become biased away from the nucleus and towards the tail. This issue was mitigated using the comet-specific, zero aperture extrapolation method [52, 53]. Astrometry was reported to the Minor Planet Center, ensuring it would be available by the time of scheduling and properly included in the solution posted on the JPL Horizons database.

Spectral Modeling

Gas production rates (Q) and rotational temperatures (T_{rot}), were derived as a function of distance from the nucleus for H_2O , CO_2 , and CO , using optimal estimation routines as part of the Planetary Spectrum Generator (PSG [15], based on synthetic fluorescence models described by Villanueva et al. [54]). To take advantage of the spatial information in our dataset, our modeling strategy followed a similar “ Q -curve” formalism to that used by previous JWST cometary studies [5, 55]. Pixels close to the nucleus are affected by PSF-related flux losses and (for stronger lines), opacity effects, which are difficult to accurately model. We therefore derived gas production rates as a function of ρ within successive $0.2''$ -wide annuli, centered on the brightest (pseudo-nucleus) pixel. Assuming uniform, isotropic gas production with a constant outflow velocity (v_{out}), the Q value converges to an asymptote, or terminal Q value (Q_t), at a characteristic ρ value, at which point the unmodelled flux losses are negligible and Q_t then represents the total molecular production rate within the field of view. To avoid contamination of these results by noisier pixels at the IFU edges, the Q curves were computed up to $\rho = 1.8''$, corresponding to the $3.6''$ -diameter circular integration apertures used in Figure 2. The gas outflow velocity was set to 0.310 km s^{-1} for H_2O and CO_2 , and 0.345 km s^{-1} for CO , based on contemporaneous observations of the spectrally resolved HCN and CO line shapes, using the ALMA Atacama Compact Array (see ALMA Observations section). Molecular photolysis rates appropriate

for the active Sun were incorporated from ref. [56]. The spectral resolution for each NIRSPEC grating (as a function of wavelength) was taken from the dispersion curves available at <https://jwst-docs.stsci.edu>.

Statistical 1σ parameter uncertainties were derived from the diagonal elements of the fit covariance matrix, scaled according to the square root of the reduced chi-square (χ_R^2) to ensure the baseline noise level was realistically accounted for. For all species apart from CO₂ the spectral baseline shape (with contributions due to scattered sunlight and thermal emission from the coma dust and nucleus, combined in some cases with instrumental artifacts), was determined by fitting a polynomial function simultaneously with the gas emission lines. This way, statistical uncertainties in the baseline shape are propagated into the final uncertainties on each Q value. For CO₂, the inaccurate model fit to some of the higher- J CO₂ lines (possibly due to the presence of multiple T_{rot} components or non-LTE effects), results in the baseline fit becoming skewed in the direction of the fit residuals. Therefore, prior to performing the CO₂ Q -curve analysis, it was necessary to subtract a fitted linear baseline from these data pixel-by-pixel (with the CO₂ + ¹³CO₂ line-containing region masked between 4.20–4.44 μm). Due to the high CO₂ line-to-continuum ratio (~ 200), uncertainties in the baseline placement for this species have negligible impact on its retrieved production rate.

When fitting individual isotopologues, PSG reports total production rates summed over all isotopologues assuming terrestrial isotopic abundance ratios. Therefore, to obtain individual isotopologue Q values, it was necessary to multiply the PSG results by the terrestrial abundance fractions, given at <https://hitran.org/docs/iso-meta/>.

The H₂O band at 2.7 μm (in the G235H setting) contains multiple, high-SNR, spectrally resolved rovibrational lines of the ortho (o) and para (p) H₂O spin states (with H-atom spins parallel *vs.* antiparallel, respectively), so this band was used to determine $T_{rot}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and the H₂O ortho-to-para ratio (OPR) — key parameters for reliably measuring $Q(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ from the weaker, more blended 4.5–5.1 μm H₂O hot bands that were observed simultaneously with HDO in the G395H setting. We modeled o- and p-H₂O simultaneously, but as separate species, allowing $Q(\text{o-H}_2\text{O})$, $Q(\text{p-H}_2\text{O})$, and T_{rot} to vary as free parameters, and with a 7th order polynomial baseline. An example of the spectral fit quality is shown in Extended Data Fig. 4.

The terminal (asymptotic) p-H₂O production rate is $Q_t = (3.79 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{26} \text{ s}^{-1}$, while for o-H₂O, $Q_t = (1.04 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{27} \text{ s}^{-1}$, leading to $\text{OPR} = 2.74 \pm 0.03$, with a total (terminal) water production rate $Q_t(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = (1.42 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{27} \text{ s}^{-1}$, summed over the ortho and para contributions. Due to the large o- and p-H₂O emission line strengths compared with the continuum around 2.7 μm , these results are not significantly dependent on the choice of baseline polynomial order. The 3I/ATLAS OPR is consistent with a spin temperature of $T_{spin} \approx 35 \text{ K}$ [57]. The fact that the associated H₂O rotational temperature of $14.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ K}$ is considerably smaller than the spin temperature, implies that the H₂O OPR is not being dictated by T_{rot} . Furthermore, constancy of the OPR as a function of radius indicates that it is not being significantly altered within the coma, and instead reflects conditions associated with the release of water from the nucleus.

The H₂O hot bands around 5 μm contained insufficient unblended lines for a reliable T_{rot} and OPR retrieval, but since they were observed simultaneously with HDO, the hot band lines were used to derive $Q_t(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ for direct comparison with $Q_t(\text{HDO})$. For the H₂O hot band (and HDO), the OPR was fixed at 2.74 and the rotational temperature for each annulus ($T_{rot}(\rho)$) was held fixed according to the $T_{rot}(\rho)$ values previously derived from the H₂O 2.7 μm band. Many of the H₂O hot-band lines in our data are blended with lines from CO, CN and OCS, so to derive $Q(\text{H}_2\text{O})$, we focused on the 4.5–4.7 μm region, which contains three of the stronger, unblended H₂O lines (see Fig. 2a). Prior to fitting the H₂O spectrum in each annulus, we subtracted the interloping CO lines, using a set of independent Gaussian fits, to facilitate identification of the spectral baseline. The spectral regions within the boundaries of each subtracted CO line (see Fig. 2a) were further masked to prevent any remaining CO line residuals from biasing the fit. The resulting $Q_\rho(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ curve is shown in Extended Data Fig. 1a. Taking the average of the outer 5 annuli gives $Q_t(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = (1.64 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{27} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is 15% larger than the value obtained from the G235H setting on the previous day, indicative of moderate temporal evolution in 3I/ATLAS’s activity.

Four individual rovibrational lines of HDO were clearly detected, as part of the ν_1 band between $\lambda = 3.55\text{--}3.85 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 2b). No evidence for other significant emission lines, including OH prompt emission, could be identified in this spectral region. A possible weak line of H₂CO could be present at 3.689 μm , just to the red of the 3.692 μm HDO line, but H₂CO contamination of the HDO signal is expected to be negligible, considering that the expected (stronger) H₂CO lines between 3.58–3.61 μm are not readily apparent in our data. Due to a relatively complex continuum shape in this region, a 7th-order polynomial was required to obtain a good fit to the baseline. The HDO rotational temperature within a $d = 3''$ circular aperture ($16 \pm 3 \text{ K}$) was found to be consistent with that of H₂O at 2.7 μm , which justifies the application of the $T_{rot}(\rho)(\text{H}_2\text{O}; 2.7 \mu\text{m})$ values during the HDO fitting. Taking the average of the outer 5 annuli of the Q -curve (Extended Data Fig. 1a) results in $Q_t(\text{HDO}) = (3.20 \pm 0.19) \times 10^{25} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This corresponds to $Q_t(\text{HDO})/Q_t(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = (1.95 \pm 0.13) \times 10^{-2}$, or D/H = $(0.98 \pm 0.06)\%$ (taking into account the number of hydrogen atoms in H₂O).

To determine $Q_\rho(\text{CO}_2)$ and $T_{rot}(\rho)(\text{CO}_2)$, the continuum-subtracted NIRSpect data cube was simultaneously fit for CO₂ and ¹³CO₂ components in the range 4.15–4.50 μm . These values were then held fixed to derive $Q_\rho(^{13}\text{CO}_2)$ using the non-continuum-subtracted cube (confined within the spectral range 4.34–4.50 μm), but this time including a variable polynomial baseline in the PSG retrieval. Continuum definition is nontrivial in the vicinity of the ¹³CO₂ band due to the presence of a relatively broad, unidentified spectral feature on the long-wavelength side of the ¹³CO₂ P-branch (around 4.42 μm), combined with the close proximity of the main CO₂ band on the short-wavelength side of the Q-branch, for which the high- J lines are not accurately modeled. We therefore investigated the effects of continuum uncertainty on $Q_t(^{13}\text{CO}_2)$ by generating an ensemble of Q -curve fits, each with a different polynomial baseline order (between 1–5). Due to potential contamination of the ¹³CO₂ P-branch by the aforementioned unidentified spectral feature, we also performed a separate ensemble of fits, masking the region between $\lambda = 4.380\text{--}4.445 \mu\text{m}$ (to exclude the ¹³CO₂ P-branch

as well as the unidentified feature). The resulting range of fitted baselines is shown in Extended Data Fig. 3a. The corresponding $Q_t(^{13}\text{CO}_2)$ values (and associated $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios) for each of the fitted baselines are shown in Table 2, along with the reduced χ^2 values (χ_R^2) for the (model minus fit) residuals. From the best-fitting $Q_t(\text{CO}_2)$ value of $(1.76 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{27} \text{ s}^{-1}$ combined with the range of possible $Q_t(^{13}\text{CO}_2)$ values, we derive $Q_t(\text{CO}_2)/Q_t(^{13}\text{CO}_2) = 141\text{--}191$ (including the 1σ statistical error margins on each retrieved measurement).

The region between $\lambda = 4.5\text{--}5.1 \mu\text{m}$ contains the strong $v = 1 - 0$ band of CO, in addition to a blend of ^{13}CO , H_2O , CN and OCS emission features. Retrieving the $^{12}\text{CO}/^{13}\text{CO}$ ratio therefore requires careful modeling of all these features. All gases were modeled as parent species apart from CN, for which the parent scale length was taken from ref. [58]. We performed a Q -curve analysis for CO by fitting the production rates for all species as a function of ρ , in addition to retrieving $T_{\text{rot}}(\rho)(\text{CO})$ (see Extended Data Figs. 1c and 5), with a 5th-order polynomial baseline included in the PSG fit. The resulting terminal production rate was $Q_t(\text{CO}) = (3.94 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{27} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The fit to the CO $v = 1 - 0$ band is very good apart from in the highest- J CO lines, some of which are blended with lines of ^{13}CO (Fig. 2e). Therefore, to retrieve $Q_\rho(^{13}\text{CO})$, we focused on the $\lambda = 4.71\text{--}5.05 \mu\text{m}$ region (which contains 15 individual lines of ^{13}CO), with the poorly-fitting higher- J CO lines masked out so that those regions did not influence the fit (see Fig. 2f). We performed the Q -curve analysis for ^{13}CO by fixing the rotational temperatures according to the previously retrieved $T_{\text{rot}}(\rho)(\text{CO})$ curve, with polynomial baseline orders between 1–5; in each case, the polynomial coefficients were optimised during fitting so that their uncertainties propagated into the final error estimates on $Q_\rho(^{13}\text{CO})$. The resulting range of fitted baselines is shown in Extended Data Fig. 3b. Due to the weakness of the lines, the ^{13}CO signal became too noisy toward the edge of the field of view, so the last two annuli were omitted from the ^{13}CO Q -curve analysis (Extended Data Fig. 1c). The best-fitting $Q_t(^{13}\text{CO})$ value and associated $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio and χ_R^2 for each baseline order is given in Table 3, corresponding to a range of $^{12}\text{CO}/^{13}\text{CO}$ values between 123–172 (including 1σ statistical error margins).

Taking the average of the last 5 points in the Q -curves for CN and OCS, from our fits to the $\lambda = 4.5\text{--}5.1 \mu\text{m}$ region, the resulting $Q_t(\text{CN})$ and $Q_t(\text{OCS})$ values for each baseline order are given in Table 3. Averaged over the set of 5 different baseline orders, we derive $Q_t(\text{CN}) = (3.10 \pm 0.6) \times 10^{24} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $Q_t(\text{OCS}) = (4.70 \pm 0.49) \times 10^{24} \text{ s}^{-1}$, where the errors are the average statistical uncertainties combined in quadrature with the standard deviations of the respective Q_t values (across the 5 different baseline orders). $Q_t(\text{CN})$ should be considered a strict lower limit because CN is produced in the comae of Solar System comets with a radial scale length $\sim 3 \times 10^4 \text{ km}$ [59], so the majority of its production is expected to occur outside of the NIRSpec field of view.

The measured OCS/ CO_2 production rate ratio is $(0.27 \pm 0.03)\%$. This is significantly less than the values of 0.6–0.9% found in comet 67P/Churyumov-Gerasimenko [60], and may indicate a relatively low elemental S/O value for the 3I/ATLAS originating system.

ALMA Observations

Submillimeter interferometric observations of comet 3I/ATLAS were obtained with the Atacama Compact Array (ACA) sub-component of the Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array (ALMA) as part of ALMA project 2025.A.00004.S. The observations were conducted in nominal Band 7 weather conditions on 2025-Dec-22 between UT 07:32–08:36, using 11×7 m antennas, with a median zenith precipitable water vapour column of 0.33 mm. The Band 7 receiver was configured to simultaneously observe the CO $J = 3 - 2$ line at 345795.990 MHz at a spectral resolution of 122 kHz and the HCN $J = 4 - 3$ line at 354505.477 MHz at a spectral resolution of 61 kHz. The position and radial velocity of the object were tracked using JPL Horizons solution #44. The interferometric data were flagged and calibrated in the Common Astronomy Software Applications (CASA) package [61] using standard scripts supplied by the Joint ALMA Observatory. The interferometric point-spread function was then deconvolved from the spectral image data using the CASA `tclean` Hogböm algorithm with natural weighting, using a mask size equal to the primary beam FWHM and stopping at a threshold of twice the RMS noise. The resulting (2D Gaussian) beam FWHM was $5.08'' \times 3.37''$ for CO and $4.91'' \times 3.28''$ for HCN.

The molecular spectra were extracted from the CO and HCN integrated emission peak position, then subjected to modeling using the SUBLIME radiative transfer code [62], in order to derive the gas outflow velocities (v_{out}). The latest theoretical state-to-state collisional rates were used for H₂O–CO [63] and H₂O–CN [64], with photolysis rates for the active Sun [56] and solar pumping rates from refs. [62, 65]. For the HCN $J = 4 - 3$ line, hyperfine components were included as described by Cordiner et al. [66]. Our calculations assumed $Q_t(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = 1.7 \times 10^{27} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $T_{kin} = 40 \text{ K}$ (based on $T_{rot} = 40.3 \pm 0.3 \text{ K}$ retrieved from our JWST CO data within a $d = 3''$ circular aperture). Ideally, collisions with CO and CO₂ should also be considered in the SUBLIME molecular excitation calculation, but in reality, the retrieved outflow velocities are not affected by the assumed collision rates. Because the gas coma of 3I/ATLAS is larger than the maximum recoverable scale for the ACA ($\sim 19''$), interferometric flux losses were modeled by applying a constant flux loss factor of 0.75 for the central beam, which was derived by comparing the peak flux of our model CO image before and after processing it using the CASA `simobserve` task.

Assuming a spherically-symmetric coma, the best-fitting SUBLIME models gave $v_{out}(\text{CO}) = 0.345 \pm 0.010 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; $Q(\text{CO}) = (2.64 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{27} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and $v_{out}(\text{HCN}) = 0.276 \pm 0.015 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; $Q(\text{HCN}) = (6.75 \pm 0.54) \times 10^{24} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (see Extended Data Fig. 2). These gas outflow velocities are smaller than the values $\sim 0.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ typically found in comets at similar heliocentric distances, which can be explained as a result of outgassing driven by a species with a higher molecular weight than H₂O [3]. This is consistent with the high CO₂/H₂O and CO/H₂O abundances (greater than unity) measured in 3I/ATLAS by JWST and ALMA, implying that CO and CO₂ sublimation are the main drivers of outgassing in this comet. Since the region of the coma where the gases are accelerated (close to the nucleus) is typically in collisional equilibrium [67], different molecules are expected to share a common outflow velocity. Differences could occur as a result of angular variations in the coma composition, or a different balance of production rates from nucleus *vs.* icy grain sublimation for different species.

Therefore, to model our JWST CO₂ and H₂O data (for which spectrally resolved line profiles were not available), we take the average of the CO and HCN outflow velocities: $v_{out} = 0.310 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, while the observed value of $v_{out} = 0.345 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ was used for CO. Ultimately, the use of the Q -curve formalism for deriving isotopic ratios helps minimize optical depth effects, such that uncertainties in v_{out} have a linear effect on our presented absolute molecular production rates. Consequently, v_{out} uncertainties should have negligible impact on the retrieved isotopic ratios.

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- **Data Availability:** All JWST data are available through the Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes at the Space Telescope Science Institute under proposal ID #5094 (<https://doi.org/10.17909/1jvn-1z72>). This work makes use of ALMA data set ADS/JAO.ALMA#2025.A.00004.S, which is available for download from the ALMA Science Archive (<http://almascience.nrao.edu/aq/>). All

scripts and data required to reproduce the results of this study are available for download from Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20531681> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20531500>)

- **Code Availability:** The JWST Calibration Pipeline software [50] is available from <https://github.com/spacetelescope/jwst>. The Planetary Spectrum Generator [15], used for modeling cometary infrared emission lines is available at <https://psg.gsfc.nasa.gov/>. The `jwstComet` software [68], used for extracting spectra from JWST data cubes and modeling them with PSG, is available from <https://github.com/apertureSynthesis/jwstComet>. The 1D version of the SUBLIME radiative transfer code [62], used for modeling the ALMA data, is available from <https://github.com/mcordiner/sublime-d1dc>. The `sublimed1dFit` code for generating optimised spectral line models using SUBLIME is available from <https://github.com/mcordiner/sublimed1dFit>.
- **Author Contributions:** M.A.C calibrated the JWST and ALMA data, performed the NIRSpec G395H spectral extraction and modeling, and led the manuscript writing. N.X.R. and G.V. contributed to the data analysis methodology, performed the G235H (2.7 μm) H₂O band modeling, and independently checked the isotopic ratio retrievals. C.O.C. obtained astrometric images using the APO. M.M. performed astrometric measurements. D.F. calculated the 3I/ATLAS orbit and ephemeris. S.B.C. helped interpret the isotopic ratios. N.B., D.B.-M., D.B., J.C., M.N.D., K.F., M.S.P.K., S.N.M., J.W.N., C.O., M.E.S. and C.A.T. helped with the project design, data acquisition, interpretation of results, and editing of the manuscript.
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Extended Data

Extended Data Figure 1: Measured production rate (Q) curves. Best fitting production rates for H_2O , CO_2 , CO and their minor isotopologues, as a function of sky-projected distance from the nucleus (ρ). Spectra were extracted and modeled within successive $0.2''$ -thick annuli centered on the coma flux peak to generate Q_ρ . For $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ and ^{13}CO , the models included a 5th-order polynomial baseline fit. Vertical error bars indicate 1σ statistical uncertainties, while the horizontal error bars indicate the radial extent of each spatial region.

Extended Data Figure 2: 3I/ATLAS ALMA spectra. High-resolution submillimeter-wave spectra of (a) CO and (b) HCN line emission from 3I/ATLAS, observed using the ALMA ACA on 2025-Dec-22. Spectra were extracted at the common emission peak for both species, and are plotted on a velocity scale with respect to the rest frequencies of the CO $J = 3 - 2$ and HCN $J = 4 - 3$ lines, respectively. Best fitting spectral models are overlaid, consistent with an average terminal H₂O OPR of 2.74 ± 0.03 .

Extended Data Figure 3: 3I/ATLAS JWST spectra with a range of baselines fits. Spectra observed in the vicinity of (a) the $^{13}\text{CO}_2 \nu_3$ band and (b) the $^{13}\text{CO } v = 1 - 0$ band, integrated within a $d = 3.6''$ circular aperture. The ensemble of best-fitting polynomial baselines considered as part of our spectral modeling is overlaid, corresponding to the $Q_t(^{13}\text{CO}_2)$ and $Q_t(^{13}\text{CO})$ values shown in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. For those fits labeled ‘m’ in panel (a), the potentially contaminated region between $\lambda = 4.380\text{--}4.445 \mu\text{m}$ (highlighted in grey) was excluded (masked) during fitting. For both panels, the “total model” curves are for the minimum χ_R^2 model (using a 5th order baseline in both cases). For ^{13}CO , numerous emission lines from additional species are present (see Fig. 2f for details).

Extended Data Figure 4: 3I/ATLAS JWST H₂O 2.7 μm spectral fit. NIR-Spec observations from 2025-Dec-22, extracted inside a $d = 3.0''$ circular aperture, with independent ortho- and para-H₂O spectral fits overlaid.

Extended Data Figure 5: Best-fitting molecular rotational temperatures (T_{rot}) as a function of ρ . Rotational temperatures were retrieved independently for each gas as a function of sky-projected distance from the nucleus (ρ). Vertical error bars indicate 1σ statistical uncertainties, while the horizontal error bars indicate the radial extent of each spatial region.

Extended Data Table 1: 3I/ATLAS
Observed Gas Production Rates

Gas	Band ID	Wavelength (μ)	Q_t (10^{25} s^{-1})
H ₂ O	$\nu_1 + \nu_3$	2.7	142 ± 1
H ₂ O	Hot bands	4.6	164 ± 5
HDO	ν_1	3.6	3.20 ± 0.19
CO ₂	ν_3	4.3	176 ± 1
¹³ CO ₂	ν_3	4.4	0.94–1.22
CO	$v = 1-0$	4.7	394 ± 1
¹³ CO	$v = 1-0$	4.8	2.49–2.99
OCS	ν_3	4.9	0.47 ± 0.05
CN	$v = 1-0$	4.9	> 0.31

Notes — Gas production rates (Q_t) in molecules per second, are averaged between $\rho = 0.8-1.8''$ to mitigate opacity effects from the inner coma, apart from ¹³CO, which was averaged between $\rho = 0.4-1.4''$ due to its weaker lines (see Methods). Errors on Q_t are the 1σ statistical model-fitting uncertainties. For ¹³CO and ¹³CO₂, the Q_t ranges correspond to the ensemble of best-fitting values across a range of plausible baseline models, and include the (additive) statistical uncertainties.

Extended Data Table 2: ¹³CO₂
terminal gas production rates and
¹²CO₂/¹³CO₂ ratios for different
baseline fit orders

Order	Q_t (¹³ CO ₂) (10^{25} s^{-1})	χ_R^2	¹² C/ ¹³ C
1	1.22 ± 0.03	9.956	144 ± 3
2	1.10 ± 0.02	6.847	161 ± 3
3	1.15 ± 0.02	4.228	154 ± 3
4	1.05 ± 0.02	3.853	168 ± 4
5	1.02 ± 0.02	3.022	172 ± 4
1(m)	1.11 ± 0.02	13.70	158 ± 3
2(m)	1.10 ± 0.02	10.74	161 ± 3
3(m)	0.97 ± 0.02	6.759	182 ± 4
4(m)	0.95 ± 0.02	7.218	186 ± 4
5(m)	0.94 ± 0.02	3.536	187 ± 4

Note — (m) indicates the fit was performed with the ¹³CO₂ P-branch masked between $\lambda = 4.380-4.445 \mu\text{m}$ to avoid baseline contamination.

Extended Data Table 3: $^{12}\text{CO}/^{13}\text{CO}$ ratios and ^{13}CO , CN and OCS terminal gas production rates for different baseline fit orders

Order	$Q_t(^{13}\text{CO})$ (10^{25} s^{-1})	$Q_t(\text{CN})$ (10^{24} s^{-1})	$Q_t(\text{OCS})$ (10^{24} s^{-1})	χ_R^2	$^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$
1	2.90 ± 0.22	3.18 ± 0.07	5.36 ± 0.26	1.761	136 ± 10
2	2.99 ± 0.22	3.11 ± 0.07	4.92 ± 0.26	1.702	133 ± 10
3	2.69 ± 0.21	3.12 ± 0.07	4.18 ± 0.26	1.562	147 ± 12
4	2.53 ± 0.21	3.07 ± 0.07	4.72 ± 0.27	1.463	156 ± 13
5	2.49 ± 0.21	3.05 ± 0.07	4.32 ± 0.29	1.426	158 ± 14

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Supplementary Information

Isotopic Evidence for a Cold and Distant Origin of 3I/ATLAS

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Supplementary Discussion

Comparison with Other Isotopic Observations of 3I/ATLAS

Our observed isotopic ratios for 3I/ATLAS ($D/H = (0.98 \pm 0.06)\%$ and $^{12}C/^{13}C = 123\text{--}172$) using JWST, are extremely unusual with respect to previous measurements of comets and other Solar System bodies (see Main Text Figure 3). Nevertheless, our results are quantitatively supported by two independent studies of 3I/ATLAS using the Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array (ALMA) and Very Large Telescope (VLT). Salazar Manzano et al. [1] used ALMA ACA observations of the HDO 241.6 GHz rotational line on 2025-Nov-04 (when 3I/ATLAS was close to perihelion, at $r_H = 1.4$ au), to derive $D/H > 0.66\%$ (at 99% statistical confidence), incorporating an upper limit for the water production rate from ACA observations of the 183.3 GHz H_2O line. Although a simultaneous H_2O observation was lacking (leading to only a lower limit for D/H), their result remains consistent with the extremely high D/H found later (at $r_H = 2.4$ au) using JWST. The two sets of HDO observations, obtained using separate telescopes operating in two different wavelength regimes, taken 49 days apart (spanning a factor of up to $\sim 10^2$ in total H_2O production rate of the object — see this study and ref. [2]), demonstrate a consistently high D/H over a large range of r_H . This supports our finding that the 3I/ATLAS nucleus has an intrinsically elevated D/H , which is not strongly affected by activity-dependent isotopic fractionation [*e.g.* 3, 4] or other biases. The conclusions of [1] are also in agreement with our study concerning the requirement of very low temperatures to produce elevated D/H ratios during interstellar (or prestellar/protostellar) ice formation.

Opitom et al. (manuscript submitted) derived a $^{12}C/^{13}C$ ratio of 147^{+87}_{-40} for 3I/ATLAS using VLT UVES spectroscopy of CN fluorescent emission around 387 nm. Due to the weakness of the observed CN isotopic lines, their resulting error bars are somewhat larger than we obtained in the infrared (for CO and CO_2) using JWST. Their range of possible values fully overlaps with our observed $^{12}C/^{13}C$ ranges, thus corroborating our results, and showing that the cause of the ^{13}C enrichment can occur at a similar rate for CO, CO_2 and CN, despite the different chemical formation pathways (and associated isotopic fractionation mechanisms) operating for these three molecules. Higher signal-to-noise observations of all three isotopologue ratios will be worthwhile in the future, to investigate the possibility of differential ^{13}C fractionation among the different gases incorporated into interstellar objects (and Solar System comets). Opitom et al. (manuscript submitted) also observed a lower $^{14}N/^{15}N$ ratio in 3I/ATLAS than previous Solar System comets. This further supports our conclusion that the ISO originated in a relatively low metallicity environment that may have been depleted in ^{15}N in addition to the observed ^{13}C depletion.

Isotopic Insights into the Origin of 3I/ATLAS

The elemental abundances observed in 3I/ATLAS place strict requirements on the chemical profile of its originating star-system, which, combined with dynamical constraints from the object's Galactic orbit (deduced from its inbound velocity vector), result in a set of criteria that help isolate its origin in space and time. Supplementary Table 1 summarises the evidence for a cold and (temporally) distant origin, explained in more detail in this subsection.

Taken at face value, the high CO and CO_2 gas production rates, as well as substantial abundances of organic molecules (including CH_3OH , H_2CO and CH_4 [5, 6] relative to H_2O provide evidence for a carbon- (and oxygen-) rich originating system. Furthermore, since rocky planets and planetesimals can only form in the presence of relatively high metal abundances (character-

ized by a logarithmic $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ abundance $\gtrsim -0.6$ relative to the Sun [7, 8]), moderately high overall metallicity is also required. Both these criteria can be fulfilled by an early burst of massive star formation (within a few giga-years of the Galaxy’s formation), followed by a slower period of further enrichment of carbon (and other elements) by low-mass AGB stellar outflows. According to the Galactic chemical evolution model of Kobayashi et al. [9], elevated interstellar $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios $\gtrsim 130$ can be achieved at relatively high (but still subsolar) metallicity ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -0.2$ to -0.6) under such a scenario. In the Galactic bulge and “thick disk” stellar populations, above-average metallicity and below-average $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios occur as a consequence of early, rapid star formation, followed by slower ^{13}C enrichment due to the relative lack of intermediate-mass (IM) AGB stars (with between 4–8 solar masses). Since nitrogen and ^{13}C are both produced more efficiently in IM AGB stars, *via* the CNO cycle [10], deficiencies of both these elements are expected to correlate. The low NH_2 and HCN abundances [5, 11], along with our low HCN/CO ratio (see ALMA Observations section and ref. [12]), could imply a deficiency of elemental nitrogen in 3I/ATLAS relative to C and O. This may therefore also be consistent with the formation of 3I/ATLAS in an environment subject to early, rapid star formation, resulting in enriched interstellar C and O abundances relative to the initial (Big Bang) abundances, but prior to the attainment of the level of ^{13}C and N enrichment typically seen in the present-day Solar System and local Galaxy.

Although the models of Kobayashi et al. [9] indicate that high $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios (up to 140) can be most readily achieved at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \gtrsim -0.6$ in the Galactic bulge, the high velocity dispersion of bulge stars ($\sim 150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) is inconsistent with the present orbit of 3I/ATLAS, which matches better with stars in the Galactic disk [13, 14]. On the other hand, the elemental composition may be consistent with the large population of old stars with elevated C/N and α/Fe ratios, identified by Masseron & Gilmore [15]¹. This chemically-defined stellar population has a higher average vertical motion than non- α -enhanced stars, but remains distinct from the classical “thick disk” stellar component [16]. However, the high vertical motion of 3I/ATLAS’s Galactic trajectory is entirely consistent with Masseron & Gilmore [15]’s old, low-metallicity, α -enhanced population ([14, 17] and M. Hopkins 2026, private communication).

In a sample of 63 nearby solar-type stars, [18] obtained $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios in the range 71–105. Based on their ages, which range between ~ 0 –9 Gyr, [19] inferred a relatively rapid onset of ^{13}C enrichment during the first 4 Gyr of our Galaxy’s evolution, as a result of ^{13}C production in novae. The resulting, steep $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ curve at early times in their model with 3–8 M_{\odot} white-dwarf nova progenitors (see Supplementary Figure 1), constrains the isotopic age of 3I/ATLAS to the range 11–12 Gyr, assuming an origin in the nearby Galactic disk. For comparison, the secondary $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ peak at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.5$ in the Kobayashi et al. [9] Fig. 19 (thick-disk model), corresponds to a similar estimated age of ~ 11 Gyr.

Uncertainties in the modeled $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios as a function of time are significant due to incomplete knowledge of the stellar initial mass function, star formation rates as a function of time (and Galactocentric radius), gas infall/outflow rates and stellar nucleosynthetic yields. A conclusive age estimate for 3I/ATLAS is further complicated by the interstellar $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ gradient as a function of Galactocentric distance (R_{GC}) [20, 21]. Although definitive measurements of interstellar gas $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios comparable to the 3I/ATLAS CO_2 lower bound of 141 are lacking, extrapolation of the Luo et al. [21] trend line for HCO^+ to the outer edge of the Galaxy ($R_{GC} = 14 \text{ kpc}$) gives $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} = 116 \pm 29$. Therefore, within the uncertainties of the Galactic trend, an origin for 3I/ATLAS in the most distant, metal-depleted outer regions of the Galactic disk is also a possi-

¹Alpha (α) elements have integer multiples of four nucleons (protons + neutrons), and are synthesized inside stars through alpha capture processes. Examples include C, O, Si and S, but not N.

bility. However, it remains to be demonstrated whether such an origin could be consistent with 3I/ATLAS’s present-day trajectory. Furthermore, the observational trend (and models) presented by Yan et al. [20] reach only $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} \approx 80\text{--}120$ in the outermost disk (see Supplementary Figure 2). Based on these results, significant temporal evolution would still be required to match the 3I/ATLAS $^{12}\text{CO}_2/^{13}\text{CO}_2$ ratio, although the age estimate would potentially be shortened to $\sim 10\text{--}11$ Gyr if 3I/ATLAS formed in the outer galaxy, due to slower ^{13}C enrichment of the ISM in those regions. Ultimately, the observed range of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratios in 3I/ATLAS can be most readily explained as a result of temporal evolution of the interstellar $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio, with a possible additional contribution from the Galactic radial $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ gradient.

Insights into the Properties of the 3I/ATLAS Natal Environment from D/H

The D/H ratio for water in 3I/ATLAS demonstrates a surprisingly high deuterium enrichment compared with other (icy and non-icy) Solar System bodies and protostars within the Galaxy (see Main Text Fig. 3). Deuteration of H_2O ice in Solar System comets is theorized to occur primarily in the interstellar and pre-stellar phases, where H_2O (and HDO) are rapidly synthesized on the surfaces of dust grains at very low temperatures ($\lesssim 30$ K) through atom-atom addition reactions [22, 23]. The D/H ratio is there determined by the balance of gas and grain-surface reactions involving H, D and O atoms, initiated by the conversion of (unreactive) gas-phase HD into (highly reactive) H_2D^+ , as a result of the reaction

The rate of the reverse reaction (destroying H_2D^+) is highly sensitive to both the gas kinetic temperature (T_{kin}) and the amount of H_2 in its ortho vs. para spin states [22, 24], so the resulting H_2O deuterium enrichments become most strongly enhanced for low values of the H_2 ortho/para ratio (OPR) and T_{kin} .

There is significant diversity in water ice D/H ratios in astrochemical models due to varying assumptions regarding the physics and chemistry of star-forming environments [22, 25]. Adopting typical metallicity, temperature and radiation conditions for the nearby Milky Way, Jensen et al. [26] showed that deuteration can remain efficient in star-forming regions as long as the dust temperatures remain below 30 K, while increased ionisation rates actually accelerate the reactions responsible for deutrating H_2O . This occurs as a result of increased H_3^+ abundances, which accelerate the conversion of HD to H_2D^+ , leading to more efficient HDO production. Increased ionisation rates also reduce the ortho-to-para conversion timescale for H_2 , which further enhances the H_2D^+ deuteration pathway. They also demonstrated that increased D/H ratios $\sim 1\%$ could be achieved in the presence of a high cosmic-ray ionisation rate ($\gtrsim 10$ times the local Galactic value). Such enhanced-ionisation conditions would be expected in the vicinity of the lower-metallicity region of intense, massive star-formation indicated by the high $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio and high abundances of α elements in 3I/ATLAS. A reduced CO abundance (relative to hydrogen) in low-metallicity interstellar clouds should further enhance the HDO/ H_2O ratio (Furuya et al., in prep.), since CO acts as a chemical inhibitor on the main H_2D^+ deuteration pathway [27]. In the lower metallicity environment implied by our high observed $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio, reduced dust grain abundances would result in less-attenuated interstellar radiation fields, and therefore higher gas ionisation rates and associated warmer dust temperatures [28, 29], which can further accelerate the grain-surface chemistry required for efficient HDO formation. Although molecular ice and planetesimal formation is expected to be less efficient in reduced metallicity environments [7, 30], the HDO-rich composition

of 3I/ATLAS proves that the cold, ice-rich conditions required for cometary accretion can still be present in the well-shielded midplanes of less metal-rich disks.

Deuterium is slowly destroyed over Galactic timescales as a result of fusion reactions in stellar interiors (astration). Consequently, the elemental D/H ratio has decreased by around 40%, from its initial (Big Bang) value of $\sim 2.5 \times 10^{-5}$, to a present day value of $\sim 1.5 \times 10^{-5}$ in the local ISM [31, 32]. Since the rate of Equation 1 is linearly dependent on the HD abundance, the rate of deuteration via H_2D^+ is also expected to vary linearly with the elemental D/H value [33]. Thus, HDO/H₂O ratios in the early Galaxy can be expected to be up to $\sim 40\%$ higher than present day ratios, as a result of astration, further contributing to the elevated value in 3I/ATLAS. We therefore suggest that several physical and chemical factors associated with an old, relatively low-metallicity environment may have worked together to produce 3I/ATLAS’s elevated HDO/H₂O ratio.

Summarising the Evidence for a Cold and Distant Origin

In summary, our study identifies numerous lines of evidence that help constrain the origin of 3I/ATLAS in space and time, as summarised in Supplementary Table 1. In the table, each line of evidence is assigned a “strength” designation ((S)trong, (M)oderate, and (C)ircumstantial), based on our assessment of its veracity, and the uniqueness of the associated conclusion. The high D/H ratio and presence of abundant hypervolatiles (CO and CH₄) provide strong evidence for the formation and preservation of 3I/ATLAS’s ices at temperatures $T < 25$ K. This does not rule out the possibility that some parts of the nucleus have been subjected to higher temperatures, but a dominant component of the observed, outgassed volatiles must have been accreted and maintained at very cold temperatures to preserve frozen CO and CH₄ in the nucleus.

The strongest evidence for formation in a relatively low-metallicity environment (but still high enough to allow planetesimal formation) comes from the ¹²C/¹³C ratios in CO and CO₂, which are reliable tracers of the elemental carbon isotopic ratio in the ISM. However, formation in a ¹³C-poor pocket of gas in the nearby (or outer) Milky Way cannot be ruled out from this ratio alone. On the other hand, considering the larger stellar densities at early Galactic times (~ 10 Gyr ago, during the intense early burst of star formation referred to as “cosmic noon” [34]), an ancient origin for 3I/ATLAS is statistically likely. The high velocity (and associated old dynamical age [17]) for 3I/ATLAS also provides moderately strong evidence for an ancient origin. The presence of abundant α -elements, and theoretical results showing enhanced HDO ice formation under strongly-irradiated interstellar conditions [26] are consistent with this conclusion, but provide only weak (circumstantial) evidence in their own right. Similarly, the low HCN and NH₂ abundances, consistent with an under-abundance of elemental nitrogen, are compatible with the association of 3I/ATLAS with the old, thick-disk stellar population identified by Masseron & Gilmore [15] (again, circumstantially).

Ultimately, our incomplete knowledge of the total elemental inventory of 3I/ATLAS, combined with significant uncertainties in Galactic chemical evolution models, precludes a conclusive statement on the precise origin of 3I/ATLAS in space and time. Nevertheless, we conclude with good confidence that 3I/ATLAS has a cold and temporally/spatially distant origin. Each interstellar object provides a unique snapshot of matter from a particular location and epoch in our Galaxy’s chemical history, so further compositional measurements of 3I/ATLAS and future interstellar objects will provide valuable data towards a more complete understanding of the Milky Way’s chemical evolution. The abundance of C, H, O, N and S-bearing species in 3I/ATLAS demonstrates the existence of volatile compounds around other stars that could lead to complex, potentially prebiotic chemistry [35], during the early history of our Galaxy.

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1: Temporal evolution of the interstellar $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio as a function of Galactic age [19]. Observed ratios in 63 solar-type stars are shown (with 1σ error bars), from ref. [18]. Galactic chemical evolution models from Romano et al. [36] are plotted, implementing nova nucleosynthesis with white-dwarf progenitors in the mass range $1\text{--}8 M_{\odot}$ (black curve), and $3\text{--}8 M_{\odot}$ (blue curve). The intersection of the ranges of fit results for $^{12}\text{CO}_2/^{13}\text{CO}_2$ and $^{12}\text{CO}/^{13}\text{CO}$ in 3I/ATLAS (141–172) is shown with a shaded orange rectangle. Adapted from Romano [19] under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Supplementary Figure 2: Interstellar CS gas $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ isotopic ratios measured in the present-day Milky Way [20] (black line with gray-shaded 1σ error margins). The red \odot symbol indicates the Solar ratio. Galactic chemical evolution model results [37, 38] are also shown. The intersection of the ranges of fit results for $^{12}\text{CO}_2/^{13}\text{CO}_2$ and $^{12}\text{CO}/^{13}\text{CO}$ in 3I/ATLAS (141–172) is shown with a shaded orange rectangle, which is significantly higher than can be explained solely by the Galactic $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ gradient, necessitating the formation of 3I/ATLAS at an earlier epoch. Adapted from Yan et al. [20] under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1: Summarising the Evidence for a Cold and Distant Origin for 3I/ATLAS

Evidence for a cold origin
1(S): Large abundances of hypervolatiles (CO and CH ₄) → formation and preservation of the nucleus at $T < 25$ K.
2(S): Extremely high HDO/H ₂ O ratio → water ice formation at $T < 30$ K.
Evidence for a temporally-distant formation epoch
1(M): Very high ¹² C/ ¹³ C ratios → age > 10 Gyr [19].
2(M): Elevated D/H ratio → consistent with deuterium astration over Galactic time.
3(C): Formation of HDO in a strongly-irradiated ISM → association with a high star-formation rate environment (“cosmic noon”).
4(C): Abundant α elements → formation around the epoch of cosmic noon.
5(C): Low NH ₂ and HCN abundances → association with old, N-poor, thick-disk stars.
6(M): High velocity trajectory → large dynamical age ~ 3–11 Gyr [17].
Notes — Strength of the evidence is denoted with (S) for strong, (M) for moderate, and (C) for circumstantial.

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